

THE EVALUATION OF THE SPORT PREFERENCES AND TENDENCIES OF CHILDREN IN AMASYA, TURKEYⁱ

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Abstract:

In this study, it was aimed to determine and evaluate the sport preferences and tendencies of children towards sports branches. The study group consisted of 1077 secondary school students from 6th, 7th and 8th grades in Amasya city center. The tendency information form was applied in order to determine the students' preferences and tendencies. In the data analysis, frequency and percentage distributions for students' preferences and tendencies were taken and evaluated. In the study, it was found that 39.6% of the students did any sport activity, whereas 60.4% couldn't do any sport activity. When it comes to the tendencies of the children, it was found that football with the percentage 27.9, basketball with 16.3%, volleyball with 15.4%, handball with 6.3%, but only 8.2% of the children could play football and 6.9% could play basketball. In addition, 6.8% could play volleyball and 3.7% could play handball. On the other hand, they were busy with sports branches in the direction of their tendencies and desires in other sport branches. In conclusion, it can be said that some children were forced to do sport that they were willing and inclined to do and that they did not want and tend to.

Keywords: children, the trend of the sport branch, sport, the preference of the sport branch

1. Introduction

Sports is a tool that promotes the development of individuals' physical, mental, emotional and social perspectives, and enhances their knowledge, skills and leadership skills. Sport helps to overcome the psychological and physiological problems that people face when they discipline themselves. Sports also have positive contributions to

ⁱ The data of this study was presented in 5th Training Science Congress, held between the dates of 2nd and 4th July 2013 in Beytepe, Ankara.

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the country's economy through international friendship and peace (Açıkada and Ergen, 1990).

Participation in the sport, which is one of the ways of coping with the health problems that arise with the stress and the immobile life tempo that accompanies the evolving and changing social life, is getting more and more important day by day. The studies that draw attention to the physical, social and economic benefits of sport participation emphasize the importance of spore participation of individuals in almost all ages (Bavlu, 2009, Koşar and Demirel, 2004).

Starting from childhood, sports activities that are applied to whole life can enable sports to become a life style. It can be said that the children who started the spore at a young age strengthened their friendship ties in the society and found easy solutions to the problems of identification during childhood and youth (Muratlı, 1997).

In childhood, a well-organized physical activity program should provide a balance between the child's sport and daily activities and should be supported by the family. It has been shown that the physical activity activities arranged in coordination with the training program have no adverse effects on education and training. On the other hand, it improves the school's success by preparing the ground for self-definition and eliminating the boredom (Açıkada, 2004).

Developing technology has caused people to have a motionless life. This situation is accompanied by health problems which are one of the most significant issues of preventive physician's agenda. The importance and the number of studies aimed at increasing physical activity are increasing day by day. At the basis of these studies, participation in physical activities from early ages is aimed to reduce possible risks in older ages. On the other hand, the sports sector is growing economically and success-oriented sport participation leads to more and more children and young athletes. Providing physical activity and participation of the spore safely brings some responsibilities to all parties concerned, with priority being given to the families. The importance of physicians and other health professionals in these studies can not be ignored (Gür, 2014).

An important part of the activities of the General Directorate of Youth and Sports is carried out with young people in school age, and it is very important for students to participate in these activities. In addition, if the sport culture is formed in childhood and the sportive tendencies are considered to be evident at an early age, ensuring active participation of the students in the schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education to sports activities is very important in terms of dissemination and activation of sports. Both institutions should continue to devote their efforts to involve students in high-sport activities and provide effective incentives for students to increase their interest in sporting activities (MEB and GSGM, 2009).

Reaching success at the top level in sports has a close relationship with early orientation to sports. Timely channeling of children and young people to the areas where they will provide the greatest benefit in the future is the most important aspect of sports science (Küçük, 1997).

The purpose of this study is to determine and evaluate the tendencies of children towards sports branches and their desires.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study Group

The study group was composed of 6,7,8. There were a total of 1077 healthy volunteer students, of which 516 were male and 561 were girls.

2.2. Data Collection

Permission was obtained from Amasya Provincial National Education Directorate. The schools were identified taking into account the socio-economic status of the neighborhoods and the Student Sports Wish and Tendency Form was used to obtain the data. Forms were distributed with the permission of classroom teachers and students were provided with objective filling. At least two classes were selected at random from selected classes at each grade level. While the forms were being filled, the children were present at the beginning and were collected after being filled.

2.3. Analysis of Data

The gender of the students was assessed by taking the frequencies and percentages of all the data as to whether they were actively engaged in sports, which sports branch they were working with, and which sports branch had tendencies.

3. Findings

Table 1: The Students' Gender and Class Distributions and Sport Habits

Variables		f	%
Gender	Female	516	47,9
	Male	561	52,1
	Total	1077	100
Class	6	347	32,2
	7	376	34,9
	8	354	32,9
	Total	1077	100
Sport	Yes	426	39,6
	No	651	60,4
	Toplam	1077	100

Of the study group, 47.9% were female, 52.1% were male, and 32.2% of the study group consisted of 7th, 34.9% of the 7th, 32.9% of the 8th grade and 39% , 6 of them played sports and 60.4% couldn't play sports (Table 1).

Table 2: Current Sport Activity Tendencies of Students and Their Wishes

Active Sports Activities			Demanded Sport Activities		
Branches	f	%	Branches	f	%
Football	88	8,2	Football	301	27,9
Basketball	74	6,9	Basketball	176	16,3
Volleyball	73	6,8	Volleyball	166	15,4
Handball	40	3,7	Handball	68	6,3
Wrestling	9	0,8	Wrestling	40	3,7
Athletics	2	0,2	Athletics	40	3,7
Swimming	11	1,0	Swimming	51	4,7
Judo	7	0,6	Judo	40	3,7
Taekwondo	9	0,8	Taekwondo	33	3,1
Karate	70	6,5	Karate	26	2,4
Ski	7	0,6	Ski	25	2,3
Ping pong	8	0,7	Ping pong	22	2,0
Tennis	6	0,6	Tennis	18	1,7
Gymnastics	2	0,2	Gymnastics	16	1,5
Badminton	14	1,3	Badminton	14	1,3
Folk dances	9	0,8	Folk dances	17	1,6
Chess	1	0,1	Chess	11	1,0
Water sports	0	0,0	Water sports	11	1,0
Other	0	0,0	Other	2	0,2
Total	426	39,6	Total	1077	100

The sports branches that children actively perform and the sports branches they tend to want to do most are respectively football, 8.2%, 27.9%, basketball 6.9%, 16.3%; volleyball 6.8%, 15.4%; handball 3.7%, 6.3%; wrestling 0.8%, 3.7%; athletics 0.2%, 3.7%; swimming 1.0%, 4.7%; , judo 0.6%, 3.7%; Taekwondo 0.8%, 3.1%; karate 6.5%, 2.4%;

skiing 0,6%, 2,3%; table tennis 0,7%, 2,0%; tennis 0.6%, 1.7%; gymnastics 0.2%, 1.5%; badminton 1,3%, 1,3%; folk dances were 0.8%, 1.6%; chess 0.1%, 1.0%; water sports were determined as 0,0%, 1,0% and other 0,0,0,2%.

4. Discussion and Result

Sunay and Saraçoğlu (1997) in their research on the elements that meet the expectations of Turkish sportsmen and that are direct them towards the sport, have shown that the formation of people's tendency towards the sports and the formation of their tendencies take place within certain expectations. At the beginning of these expectations is to be healthy by doing sports, having a good physical appearance and being chosen to national team. This is very important in terms of including the efforts for the dissemination of sports in society and the fulfillment of such expectations. In the survey we conducted, there are differences between the sports branches that children actively want to involve in and the sports branches that they expect (Table 2). In addition to the branch in which the children actively play sports, it is necessary to support them by taking into account the sports branches that have expectations.

In another study, the influence of television and media on the sports orientation should be increased, as well as the evaluation of the family's views on children's sports orientation. Starting particularly with family, children are under the influence of school, teacher, media, friends group. The individual should be able to freely reflect his or her personality within the family, school and environment (Şimşek, 2005). The research done by Şimşek (2005) is parallel to our study and the children should be encouraged to make active and willing sports by informing the family, the school and the environment, which are among the factors of the children's failure to perform the sports branches they are expecting, and by removing the obstacles that prevent their expectations.

In another study, parents should be aware of their children's expectations and desires in orienting them to sports in order to be successful athletes (Keskin 2006). In the research we conducted, 1077 students were evaluated and it was seen that 39,6% of the participating students were still active in sports life and 60,4% were not actively playing sports (Table 1). It should be taken into consideration that children's active sports branches are different from the sports branches they expected to do, that the number of students who can not play sports they desired is high, that they are not fully encouraged to do sports and that differences between students who can not play sports but who are interested in and desire for different sports branches may develop health problems later on.

When the distribution in Table 2 is examined, it is seen that 27.9% of children have the desire and tendency in playing football, 16.3% in playing basketball, 15.4% in playing volleyball, and 6.3% in playing games such as handball, but it was determined that they could play games such as football (8.2%), basketball (6.9%), volleyball (6.8%) and handball (3.7%). It may be expressed that children are forced to do sports that they are not willing and tend to do, but the ones which they do not want and tend to do.

Failure to perform sports that they have expectation and tendency to with various factors, the lack of consideration of their needs and not making necessary notifications in this regard and inadequacy of studies in this regard can cause children to have serious health problems in the future and consequently increase the health expenditures. In another study, 532 students in 9th, 10th and 11th grades of high schools in Amasya city center were evaluated and it was found that 24.1% of the students were willing and expecting to play football, 11.8% basketball, 15.8% volleyball and 2.4% handball, but only 8.3% could play football, 3.4% basketball, 4.3% volleyball and 0.4% handball (Güler et al., 2014). The study made by Güler et al. (2014) and this study showed parallelism and it is expected that children should be directed towards the sports by considering their wishes and tendencies.

It is also revealed in studies that sport is one of the important factors on human development in cognitive, sensory and psycho-motor fields. In a study that examined key research in this area, they shared the results of studies conducted in the United States, about 12,000 children between 6 and 18 years of age, and studies conducted over a long period of time, and looked at how physical activity affected students' school achievement. Researchers have found that there is a link between physical activity and academic performance in their researches, and that students who are more active in the physical sense have higher academic achievement. Researchers found that exercise provided more blood and oxygen to the brain and emphasized that exercise reduced stress and balanced emotions by providing endorphins, thus improving one's cognitive system. These results point out that not only the academic content and learning, but also different fields such as physical activity can play a role in success in education (Singh et al, 2012). The biggest obstacle for students to participate in sports activities in general and GDYS (General Directorate of Youth and Sports in Turkey) activities in particular are the concerns of students towards their future. The intensity of the exams required to accomplish while shaping the future of the students and the competitive environment in this regard prevent their orientation to sports. Student parents may prevent their children from engaging in sports, even if they are skilled in specific branches of the sport (MEB and GDYS, 2009).

Factors that increase participation in physical activity among school children at elementary school level in the United States have been investigated in the study of Stucky-Ropp and Dilorenzo (1993) for children's exercise determinants, and friends and family support have been found as significant factors for boys and girls as well as having fun (Stucky-Ropp and Dilorenzo, 1993). In another study, it is said that the rate of participation of students in extracurricular activities should be increased to the desired level and that in-class and out-of-school activities should be organized in such a way as to fully meet the expectations of the students (Ayberk et al., 2011). Actually, the study results we have implemented in Amasya show that students, parents and teachers do not take much into account the importance of sports for mental development and healthy life. It is believed that the students who pass from secondary school to the high school are not able to do sports as much as they can in the traffic of

intensive courses, and those who have these possibilities also go to sports branches in the environment where they live.

As a result, it can be said that many student groups and children are forced to do sport that they are not willing and tendency towards, but to do sports that they do not have the will and tendency.

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